

Impact of Hyponatremia on Clinical Outcome in Patients with Acute Cerebrovascular Accidents

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Abstract:

Background: Acute cerebrovascular accidents (CVA) have a significant social and economic impact and ranks third in terms of morbidity and mortality after cancer and coronary heart disease. Electrolyte disturbances, particularly hyponatremia, are common in patients with acute cerebrovascular accidents which significantly worsens clinical outcomes. The main objective of this study was to estimate the different serum electrolytes, sodium, potassium and chloride and to determine the degree of hyponatremia with the clinical outcome in cerebrovascular accident patients

Material and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in department of biochemistry, S.V. medical college, Tirupati on 40 acute cerebrovascular accident patients. Serum electrolytes were estimated and outcome was measured in terms of discharge or death based on degree of hyponatremia.

Results: Out of the 40 study participants, 24 (60%) patients had altered serum sodium levels, of these 21(87.5%) had hyponatremia, 3(12.5%) had hypernatremia. Among 21 cases, 13 (61.9%) had mild, 6 (28.6%) moderate and 2 (9.5%) severe hyponatremia. The serum sodium concentration was notably decreased in the ischemic stroke (127.17 ± 6.83 mEq/L) in comparison to the hemorrhagic stroke (139.25 ± 6.73 mEq/L) with p-value: <0.001 . Whereas serum potassium level was elevated in hemorrhagic stroke (3.24 ± 0.37 mEq/L) in contrast to the ischemic stroke (3.71 ± 0.46 mEq/L) with p-value 0.02. When outcome measures (death or discharge) were stratified, the overall deaths in patients with hyponatremia were 14.28%. Of this 7.69% deaths were with mild hyponatremia, 16.7% with moderate hyponatremia and 50% with severe hyponatremia with a significant P-value <0.001 .

Discussion: Our study highlights the necessity for heightened awareness and proactive management of hyponatremia, a common electrolyte disturbance in stroke patients. Regardless of mild, moderate, or severe, it has been shown to exacerbate the clinical course of stroke patients, leading to increased morbidity, prolonged hospital stays, and higher mortality rates.

Conclusion: Hyponatremia is a critical determinant of clinical outcomes in CVA patients. Its presence significantly increases the risk of mortality, morbidity, and poor functional recovery. Early recognition and appropriate management of hyponatremia are vital to mitigate its adverse effects.

Keywords: Cerebrovascular Accidents (CVA), Hyponatremia, Serum Electrolytes.

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Introduction

Cerebrovascular accident or stroke is a major contributor to sustained disability and mortality. As per the world health organization (WHO), report of deaths due to CVA was around 85% in developing countries [1]. It is an emergency medical condition characterized by an acute compromise of the cerebral perfusion or vasculature. Cerebrovascular accidents or stroke are of two types; hemorrhagic and ischemic stroke. Ischemic stroke accounts for ap-

proximately 85% of strokes and remaining are hemorrhagic [2]. Electrolyte irregularities are often seen in newly diagnosed cerebrovascular accident cases and have a very high influence on the progress and prediction of the disease unless corrected promptly. Frequently seen electrolyte imbalances in the patients with acute cerebrovascular accidents are decreased serum levels of sodium, potassium, calcium, magnesium and phosphate. Hyponatremia

is the most prevalent electrolyte disturbance observed in patients suffering from neurological disorders like CVA [3]. When serum sodium level is <135 mEq/L, it is termed as hyponatremia and its severity is categorized as mild ($130-134$ mEq/L), moderate ($120-129$ mEq/L) and severe (<120 mEq/L). Hyponatremia is primarily hyposmolal in CVA which may be due to either syndrome of inappropriate anti-diuretic hormone (SIADH) or cerebral salt wasting syndrome (CSWS). The decrease of serum sodium level is observed most commonly in SIADH rather than in CSWS [4]. Additionally causes of hyponatremia may also be due to restricted intake of salt, use of anti-hypertensive drugs like diuretics in hypertension, and also any secondary infections. All these lead to altered sensorium and incline the patients to seizures

The Incidence of hyponatremia in stroke is stated to be 11% to 35% and the degree of mortality associated with it was found to be greatly elevated to as much as 60% [5,6,7]. Typically, hyponatremia in stroke is of the hyposmolal variety and is brought on by either SIADH or CSWS. Central nervous system (CNS) diseases, carcinomas, and pulmonary illnesses are the three disease groups where SIADH is most frequently manifested. Medications, including analgesics, antidepressants, barbiturates, carbamazepine and oral hypoglycemics potentially may also be the cause. Patients with SIADH are typically hypertensive and euvolemic [8]. The term "true hyponatremia" refers to loss of sodium primarily into the urine without any increase in the total systemic volume, which is known as CSWS. Although the underlying mechanism causing CSWS is unknown, one theory claims that it is due to excessive renal pressure natriuresis that happens as a result of elevated sympathetic nervous system [9,10]. There is scanty data as very few studies have been conducted concerning acute stroke with electrolyte disturbances. These studies revealed hyponatremia as the commonly encountered electrolyte imbalance in patients of acute stroke. However, it is yet unclear whether the proper revival of serum sodium concentrations improves the outcome in CVA. The objective of this study was to evaluate the serum sodium, potassium and chloride concentrations and to learn about the effect of hy-

ponatremia on outcome in patients with cerebrovascular accidents.

Materials and Methods:

A cross-sectional study was carried out in the department of Biochemistry, S.V. Medical college, Tirupati, after obtaining the Institutional Scientific committee and Institutional Ethics committee approval. A total of 40 patients admitted in MICU & RICU of the SVRRGGH, Tirupati diagnosed with cerebrovascular accidents/ acute ischemic stroke were recruited in the study. Patients of both genders aged above 55yrs diagnosed with stroke or cerebrovascular accident were included and patients with renal failure, on saline therapy or hemolytic disease and who were not willing to give consent for participation in the study were excluded.

The required sample size was calculated with the formula $4pq/d^2$ considering the prevalence (p) of hyponatremia in stroke or cerebrovascular accident patients as 35% and precision (d) 15% with 95% confidence interval as per a study conducted by Sheikh Saleem et al [11].

Four milliliters (4.0 mL) of venous blood was collected using standard phlebotomy technique after obtaining the written informed consent from the participants/attendants of the present study. The blood was allowed to clot at room temperature for 20-30 minutes, followed by centrifugation at 2000 RPM for 15 minutes. The supernatant serum was preserved at -20°C till further analysis was performed. The serum electrolytes, sodium, potassium and chloride were analysed by indirect ion selective electrode using ST200 Pro electrolyte analyser. Outcome was measured in terms of recovery (discharge) or death based on degree of electrolyte disturbances (mild, moderate, severe) in these CVA patients.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed using SPSS (Statistical Package of Social Sciences) software version 21. Continuous variables and categorical variables were interpreted using frequencies (mean \pm SD) and proportions (%).

Results:

Table 1: Serum electrolyte levels in Ischemic and haemorrhagic stroke patients

Serum electrolytes (mEq/L)	Ischemic stroke (Mean \pm SD)	Haemorrhagic stroke (Mean \pm SD)	p-Value
Serum sodium	127.17 \pm 6.83	139.25 \pm 6.73	<0.001
Serum potassium	3.24 \pm 0.37	3.71 \pm 0.46	0.021
Serum chloride	96.58 \pm 3.63	103.63 \pm 2.72	<0.001

The sodium concentration in serum was notably decreased in the ischemic stroke patients (127.17 ± 6.83 mEq/L) than in the patients of haemorrhagic stroke (139.25 ± 6.73 mEq/L) with a p-value <0.001 . The serum potassium concentration was

raised in the haemorrhagic stroke (3.71 ± 0.46 mEq/L) cases in contrast to the ischemic stroke (3.24 ± 0.37 mEq/L) with p-value of 0.02. When compared to the haemorrhagic stroke patients (103.63 ± 2.72 mEq/L), ischemic stroke patients

(96.58 ± 3.63 mEq/L) had remarkably lesser serum chloride level with a p-value: <0.001.

Table 2: Hyponatremia and hospital stay among stroke patients

	Frequency (%)
Age (years)	
<55	22.5
>55	77.5
Gender	
Male	70
Female	30
Stage of hyponatremia	
Mild	61.9
Moderate	28.6
Severe	9.5
Duration of hospital stay	
3days or less	27.5
4-5 days	42.5
>5 days	30

Of the 40 participants with cerebrovascular accidents who were included in the study, 22.5 % were aged <55yrs. and 77.5% were aged >55yrs. Among them 28 (70%) were males and 12 (30%) were females. Hyponatremia was found to be mild, moderate and severe in 61.9%, 28.6 % and 9.5 % of the patients respectively. Duration of hospital stay was 3days or less for 27.5%, 4-5 days for 42.5% and >5days for 30% of the study participants (Table 2)

Table 3: Outcome stratified with degree of hyponatremia

Degree of hyponatremia	Outcome		P-value
	Death	Discharge	
Mild	7.69%	92.3%	<0.001
Moderate	16.7%	83.3	
Severe	50%	50%	

Based on the degree of hyponatremia when outcome (death or discharge) was stratified, 7.69% deaths occurred due to mild, 16.7%, in moderate and 50% with severe hyponatremia of P-value <0.001.

Figure 1: Prevalence of hyponatremia among cerebrovascular accident patients

In the cerebrovascular accident patients, prevalence of hyponatremia was found to be 60%, hypernatremia was 10% and normonatremia was found to be 30%.

Figure 2: Impact of hyponatremia on outcome of cerebro vascular accident patients

Hyponatremia among stroke patients was significantly associated with mortality.

Discussion

Cerebrovascular accident/stroke is a disabling illness and is one of the principle causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Globally burden of stroke is increasingly credited to preventable and non-preventable risk factors. Stroke patients having associated comorbidities like diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and congestive cardiac failure are more prone to develop electrolyte disturbances.

Hyponatremia is one of the most prevalent acute electrolyte abnormalities in cerebrovascular accident patients. It worsens the course of the disease by simulating the symptoms of an underlying neurological impairment. In this study the prevalence of hyponatremia was found to be 60% among the stroke patients (fig 1), which is almost similar to the study conducted by Shah A et al which showed a prevalence of 66.5% [12]. The study conducted by Rodrigues et al also found that higher incidence of hyponatremia is seen in SIADH patients (58%), one of the common causes for cerebrovascular accidents [13].

Our study found that among the patients with hyponatremia, the ischemic stroke group had a decreased level of serum sodium and the patients of hemorrhagic stroke had increased level of serum potassium, whereas serum chloride levels were significantly lower in ischemic stroke patients when compared to hemorrhagic stroke patients. These results are similar with the work conducted by Rodrigues et al. and Soiza et al who documented that patients with decreased level of serum sodium (hyponatremia) were more susceptible to develop severe stroke and had higher risk of landing in death [13,14]. In contrast research work by Christensen et al. and Farahmand et al. revealed that

hypernatremia was associated with increased incidence of stroke and lead to aggravation of the neurological conditions [15,16]. The present study revealed that stroke is predominantly seen in the age group >55yrs which coincides with the study conducted by Hasaan H. Musa et al, the common age group affected being 41-60yrs (42.55%) followed by 61-80yrs (40.96%) [17]. In terms of gender, 70% were male and 30% were female patients, showing that men were more at risk of developing cerebrovascular accidents than women.

Similar outcomes were also observed, though not to a greater extent in UK, USA, Italy, Saudi Arabia, Germany and Spain etc. Our study also showed that 24 (60%) patients had altered serum sodium level. Of them 21(87.5%) had hyponatremia, 3(12.5%) had hypernatremia. Out of 21 hyponatremia cases, 13(61.9%) had mild hyponatremia which coincided with the study done by Ehtesham M et al [18]. Hyponatremia is a prognostic factor for various clinical outcomes and mortality in patients suffering from cerebrovascular accidents. In our study the overall mortality in CVA patients with hyponatremia is 14.28%, showing that the degree of hyponatremia is significantly associated with mortality. This is in accordance with study done by Kidwai AA et al [11].

The degree of hyponatremia significantly correlates with mortality rates in patients experiencing acute cerebrovascular accidents (CVAs). Mild Hyponatremia (130-134 mEq/L) can increase the risk of adverse outcomes and may have a higher likelihood of complications, though the increase in mortality risk is generally less pronounced compared to more severe cases. Severe Hyponatremia is strongly associated with the highest mortality rates among stroke patients. This condition can cause severe neurological symptoms, including seizures, coma, and substantial cerebral edema, which can be life-

threatening without prompt and effective treatment. The impact of hyponatremia on mortality in stroke patients underscores the importance of routine electrolyte monitoring and timely correction of sodium imbalances to improve clinical outcomes and reduce mortality risks.

Conclusion

In conclusion, hyponatremia significantly impacts clinical outcomes in patients with acute cerebrovascular accidents (CVAs), commonly known as stroke. Hyponatremia is associated with heightened morbidity, prolonged hospital stays, poor functional recovery and mortality. Early detection and appropriate management of hyponatremia are crucial to improve the clinical outcome in these patients. Integrating routine monitoring of sodium levels into the standard care protocol for stroke patients may help mitigate these adverse effects and enhance overall recovery and prognosis.

Future research should focus on optimizing treatment strategies for hyponatremia in the context of acute cerebrovascular events to further improve patient outcomes.

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